

PLOT SYSTEM OF UZBEK TOPONIMIC LEGENDS

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Abstract: It is known that, as in other genres of Uzbek folklore belonging to the epic type, the plot system of toponymic legends consists of certain traditional motifs. Motive is an element that forms the plot of any work of art, including folklore, and is often distinguished by its traditional character. It is the motifs that are the elements of the epic narrative that have become somewhat stagnant, and are characterized by their traditionality and repetitiveness.

Keywords: myth, toponym, motive, typology, classification.

Аннотация: Известно, что, как и в других жанрах узбекского фольклора эпического типа, сюжетная система топонимических легенд состоит из определенных традиционных мотивов. Мотив - элемент, образующий сюжет любого произведения искусства, в том числе фольклорного, часто отличается традиционным характером. Именно мотивы, являющиеся элементами эпического повествования, стали несколько застойными и характеризуются своей традиционностью и повторяемостью.

Ключевые слова: миф, топоним, мотив, типология, классификация.

The plot system of Uzbek folk toponymic legends consists of a complex of traditional motifs. Certain studies have also been carried out on the identification and classification of motifs in folklore works belonging to this genre. For example, according to M. Rahmonova, who has specially studied the issues of genre characteristics and poetics of legends, it is appropriate to classify the motive system of epic works belonging to this genre into the following types according to their poetic function: 1. The hero is a lost child or disciple; 2. Motifs related to the artistic image in legends express the tradition of worshiping the cult of nature (water, fire, birds and animals); 3. Misleading children; 4. Having a strange horse; 5. Having epic

sponsors; 6. Twist motive; 7. Dream motive; 8. Love motive; 9. Animistic and totemistic mythological motifs. These are traditional motifs of legends.

The question of motive and its relationship to the epic plot

Although this classification includes all types of Uzbek folk legends, it does not express the motives specific to all types of legends. For example, the appearance of certain celestial bodies in legends, as well as the hero's journey, the toponymic motif explaining the occurrence of place names, is not reflected in this classification.

In our opinion, the traditional motifs in the toponymic legends of the Uzbek people can be grouped into the following types according to their historical origin and sources:

- a) archaic motifs associated with ancient totemistic, animistic and cult myths;
- b) transformational motives formed as a result of the evolution of "Avesta" mythology and plots;
- c) traditional motives caused by the influence of sources related to the religion of Islam;
- g) "traveling plots" and adopted motifs from the folklore of other peoples through the process of mutual literary influence.

Due to the introduction of Islam to the territory of Central Asia, the "Holy Qur'an", its interpretations, hadiths, as well as the spread of various educational and literary sources in the folk art, in particular, in oral prose works belonging to the genre of legends. According to the origin, plots and motifs that go back to Islamic sources have become widely popular. The unique expression of this historical-folkloric process can be seen in the interpretation of the motive of the severed head rolling away and disappearing from sight in the toponymic legends of the Uzbek people, and the hero holding the head separated from his body in his arms. we are happy

Uzbek folk toponymic legends can be classified into the following types according to the functional-semantic features of various epic interpretations of the

motif of the rolling of the head separated from the body recorded in the construction of the plot:

a) determination of the location of the bottom of a water body (such as a river, stream); According to the legend of "Alamli", it was a very difficult matter to irrigate the crops in time due to the lack of water in the past. That is why a king named Abdullah Khan wanted to dig a canal. He shaved the head of a man who evaded work. Because the work was prolonged, the ruler asked for help from the neighboring kingdom. Then a man came riding a white camel. Abdullah Khan got angry. "It seems that this tsar has really mocked me," the executioners called, "Take his head!" - he ordered. They still took the head of the man. The head that fell on the camel kept rolling and rolling. A white camel is also dragging the body behind the head. That's why the water is making its way by itself.

b) to be the basis for determining the place where the rolled head is made in a certain monument. According to the legend "Construction of Minarai Kalon", the emir of Bukhara, Muhammad Arslan Khan, had a debate with one of the greatest sheikhs of Bukhara, Faizi Auliya, over an important issue. Saint Fayzi won the debate. Enraged, Muhammad Arslan Khan drew his sword and ran away the Saint Faizi. The body of saint Faizi remained in that place, his head rolled and fell into a depth and disappeared. From the depths came a voice like this:

- People, the emir killed me innocently, he is angry with God. So that my blessed head will not be trampled on, build such a building over my head that it will stand as long as the world stands.

Everyone heard the sound from the depths. This was also conveyed to Arslan Khan. Arslan Khan Faizi was afraid of the saint's curse and built a high minaret over his head to atone for his sin.

Analyze this legend as an example of Uzbek folk historical prose. According to M. Rahmonova, the motif of the severed head rolling up and falling into a pit, well or cave reflects our people's views on the other world. According to the mythological concept of our people, the universe consists of three parts, and a cave

or a well is imagined as a path leading to the property of the dead located underground. In the "Minorai Kalon" legend, the madman's head rolling and entering the cave means that he has gone to the underworld. Because the people who lived in ancient times believed that the cave serves as a symbolic tool that unites and connects the worlds of the earth and the underworld.

In this place, the head separated from the body rolling down and disappearing into the pit means that the upper part of the human body - the soul imagined to be located in the head - has moved to the "other world" - the "space of the dead". Here, the "deep" detail is based on the ancient mythological view of the trichotomous structure of the universe consisting of three parts, i.e. the upper (heaven), middle (ground or earth) and lower (subterranean) worlds. It is a symbol of the passage to the "other world", which is interpreted as being located underground.

c) identification of the place where the rolled head disappeared (or stopped). In some toponymic legends, it is told that the head cut off by the captives rolled away from the battlefield and the place where the head disappeared became a blessed place. In particular, the legend "Kuvkalla" recorded by the son of Rahmatulla Yusuf, who lives in the village of Karakisa, belonging to the village council of Josh, Koshrabot district of Samarkand region, is an example of this kind of epic interpretation of the motif of the head. In it, it is described that in ancient times, a hero went to Talamak Mitans. But the Mitans increased in number, chased the hero, caught up with him when he passed through To'sin, and cut off his head. After that, the severed head ran away. Mitans: "Chase, kill!" - they chased. Thus, when the hero's head exceeded the border of his village, a bunch of his fellow villagers - horsemen - got out. They sent the Mitans back. Butir's head fell into the stream and stopped. Kalla was buried here. Even now, a community respects the place where the hero is buried."

In the legend "Saron Bobo", the origin of the toponymic term with the same name is interpreted based on the motif of the head: "one day a shepherd wanted to water his sheep from this well and drove the flock. But Khoja Ubban escaped from

this healing well He didn't let them water the fields. The shepherd got angry at this situation and threw a stick at Khoja Ubban's head, causing his head to fall several miles away. The place where the body was left is Khoja Ubban, and the place where his head fell is Saron. In another version of this legend, the severed head of Khuja Ubban speaks and speaks as if he were alive: "One day, the enemies were lying in wait and when Khuja Ubban was praying, they killed him with a sword. Khwaja Ubban's body remained here, and his head began to run away. Angels appeared in front of the fleeing head and said: "Stop! When they asked, "Where are you going?", the head said, "I'm going to McCatillo!" Then, when the angels asked, "Will your body stay here?", the head disappeared right there. The place where the body was left was called Khoja Ubban, and the place where the head disappeared was called Saron Baba.

The plot of the saint walking with his severed head after being executed by the ignorant is one of the common aspects of the folklore of the peoples of the world, and the typological parallel of this plot is found in religious sources promoting Christian beliefs, including the Russian text about Zosim's cell. we can also find it in folk legends.⁶ According to the classic work of Irish folklore, "The Big Edda", Odin achieves many successes thanks to the head of the wise Mimir, because it is this head that acts as his closest advisor.

In terms of the origin and sources of this motive, which we conventionally call the "cut-off motif", there are certain opinions expressed in folklore studies. In particular, the ethnographer V. N. Basilov, who analyzed the interpretations of the beheaded motif in Islamic narratives about saints and sanctified persons and hagiographical sources in comparison with the Christian plots on the same topic, believes that the genesis of the beheaded motif recorded in Islamic legends is connected to the cult of nature that is dying and resurrecting. Researcher M. Rakhmonova also believes that "the historical basis of the motif of the hero carrying his severed head in his hands or the rolling of the severed head goes back to the cult of ancestors and mythological visions of dying gods."

In our opinion, the folklore of the Turkic peoples who believe in the religion of Islam, including the works belonging to the genres of fairy tales and legends of the Uzbek folk oral art, are the means for the emergence of traditional motifs related to a severed head or a withered skull. It seems that "Kisekbash Kitab", one of the samples of Turkish written literature, was based on it. This religious-moral and adventure-fantasy work related to the name of Hazrat Ali ibn Abu Talib was created in the 14th-15th centuries and became popular among the people mainly through the medium of storytelling. According to this story, Kisekbash is a wise and virtuous person who was once the ruler of a huge country. He turned to our prophet and said that a giant attacked his land, plundered the land and cut off his head from his body. Our Prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him, entrusts Hazrat Ali with the task of helping him. Together with Hazrat Ali Kisekbash, he goes to the desert, falls into a big old well in the middle of the desert, and destroys it with a giant. After that, our prophet resurrected Kisekbash and his son and returned to their previous state. "Jumjuma-sultan" written in Turkish by Khusam Kotib is also available.

The widespread popularity of such works, which were created in order to promote the religious and educational message related to Islam, as well as the influence of these works on the plot system of the folklore, is reflected in the Turkic folk, including the toponymic legends of the Uzbek people. There are various epic interpretations of the kesikbosh motif.

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